

Social

MOBILE CHATTING BEHAVIOUR OF ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Mobile connectivity is the order of the day. Personas irrespective of their socio-economic status possess mobile device either basic or advanced android or windows or IOS. The chat applications have become popular with younger generation. It has started trickling down to children below the age of eighteen. The behaviour has influenced the aged also. The mobile chat applications have no barriers with regard to age group, nativity, social status and economic status. The increasing dominance of these mobile chat applications need to be studied. It has been eating away our young people's time and mind. The recent election in Tamil Nadu is the best example. Parties have used these chat applications to make their comments, appeals, abuses and pleas. Wherever we go it is obvious that the students sit with mobile apps ignoring the presence of others. It has become the natural quest of everyone who is penchant in doing research to take up a study on this behaviour. Hence, the investigators have taken up this study to find out arts and science college students mobile chatting behaviour like use of chat applications, time of chatting and chatting with the people associated with them. The study has used simple random sampling technique of 300 arts and science college students of Chennai area. The findings of the study reveal that there are four chat applications namely WhatsApp, Messenger, Skype and Hang out occupying first, second, third and fourth places respectively among arts and science college students.

Keywords:

Mobile, Chatting, Behaviour, Arts and Science College Students.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Mobile connectivity is changing the way we shop, socialise and play. While this trend is helpful for many businesses and consumers, its disruption of social norms has created new challenges that we must address in order to fully capitalise on innovative technology.

According to global social marketing agency *We Are Social* more than 2 billion Asians are registered with social-media accounts, 1.7 billion of them active. From audio to video to text, technology facilitates human expression. On smart phones alone, we average 23 minutes talking, 20 minutes texting, 18 minutes emailing and 11 minutes social-networking each day, according to research from the Consumer Electronics Association (CEA). Forty –four per cent us even admit to sleeping beside our devices because we are afraid of missing calls, text messages and other updates overnight. Clearly, we're living in a day and age not just defined by mobile connectivity, but dominated and controlled by it.

Even as brands begin realising the growing potential of chat apps, these apps seem ready to take over the world. Not only are Asian-grown chat apps driving the push to take over community building and m-commerce, they're also becoming a one-stop platform for all entertainment needs - developing in-house mobile games and working with wearables and the Internet of Things (IoT).

Several chat apps are building the beta version of what's to come in the near future, with the IoT becoming a reality. It's easy to imagine a future where household appliances and errands are controlled from within chat apps, potentially freeing up time for the average consumer. From buying groceries to logging exercises to downloading media files, all of these activities could potentially be done without missing a new text from a friend.

Ultimately, nothing beats the rapport developed through face-to-face conversations, eye contact and a firm handshake. As such, chat apps aim to be as personable as possible, and even encourage interactions out of the app. For instance, both Line and WeChat allow users to create customised stickers, using their own photos. Apart from video and voice-messaging functions, which give users the ability to send voice messages or video-chat with another party, WeChat has a "People Nearby" function that encourages users to make friends with others in the vicinity.

Over the past 40 years, technology has evolved quickly, and the next 40 years will almost certainly deliver innovations at an even faster pace. The workforce will become increasingly mobile, with the majority of consumers using mobile devices for day-to-day tasks, such as grocery shopping and banking. Even as technology solutions and tools evolve, the fundamentals of communication will never change. Face-to-face interactions, personal relationships and first hand impressions still matter, especially in business

2. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Mobile connectivity is the order of the day. Personas irrespective of their socio-economic status possess mobile device either basic or advanced android or windows or IOS. The chat applications have become popular with younger generation. It has started trickling down to

children below the age of eighteen. The behaviour has influenced the aged also. The mobile chat applications have no barriers with regard to age group, nativity, social status and economic status. The increasing dominance of these mobile chat applications need to be studied. It has been eating away our young people's time and mind. The recent election in Tamil Nadu is the best example. Parties have used these chat applications to make their comments, appeals, abuses and pleas. Wherever we go it is obvious that the students sit with mobile apps ignoring the presence of others. It has become the natural quest of everyone who is penchant in doing research to take up a study on this behaviour. Hence, the investigators have taken up this study to find out arts and science college students mobile chatting behaviour like use of chat applications, time of chatting and chatting with the people associated with them.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To find out the use of chat applications by arts and science college students
- 2) To find out the time of chatting by Arts and Science College students
- 3) To find out the chatting of Arts and Science College students with the people associated with them.

4. HYPOTHESES

- 1) The arts and science college students do not use any chat applications
- 2) The time of chatting by Arts and Science College students is equally during all the time of a day.
- 3) The Arts and Science College students do chat with all the people associated with them equally.

5. TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

Arts and Science College Students - refers to UG degree students of arts and science colleges in the 10 +2+3 system of education in India.

Mobile Chatting – refers to conversation in mobile phones of ios, android and windows based with chat applications.

Behavior – refers to manners, deeds, conduct etc.

6. DELIMITATIONS AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study was confined only with arts and science college students in Chennai Metropolitan city only.

The finding of the study will reveal the use of chat applications in mobile phones by arts and science college students in Chennai only. It cannot be over generalized and considered as an overall reflection of use of chat applications of arts and science college students of other cities. However it may give an idea about use of chat applications by the age group of 18 years and above.

7. PLANNING OF THE RATING SCALE

The researcher studied the concept of use of Chat applications and surveyed with students on the availability of various chat applications. Finally he arrived at the following 10 chat applications which are familiar among arts and science college students.

- 1) Whatsapp
- 2) Messenger
- 3) Skype
- 4) Hang Outs
- 5) We Chat
- 6) Tango
- 7) Telegram
- 8) Chat on
- 9) Hike
- 10) Line

8. ESTABLISHING RELIABILITY OF THE TOOL

TEST AND RETEST METHOD

The test was administered among the 25 students and re-administered among the same 25 after of 15 days. The comparative performance and deviation were analyzed. The deviation is negligible. Hence the tool is assumed to be having reliability. Thus the reliability was ensured in the tryout.

ESTABLISHING VALIDITY OF THE TOOL

The face and content validity was established for this tool. The face and content validity was checked with Assistant Professors in computer science working in Colleges of Education in Chennai.

SCORING

The scores for each item is counted and classified in an ordinal scale.

SAMPLE

The investigator has followed simple random sampling method for the Present study. There were 300 students taken for the study. The sample is from Chennai Metropolitan city. The investigator used percentage analysis for the study.

9. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

HYPOTHESIS 1

The arts and science college students do not use any chat applications.

The details regarding use of chat applications by arts and science college students are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: PERSENTAGE ANALYSIS OF ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS USE OF CHAT APPLICATIONS

Chat Applications	No. of Students	Percentage	Ranking
Whatsapp	300	100%	1
Messenger	231	77%	2
Skype	156	52%	3
Hang Outs	56	18.6%	4
We Chat	14	0.04%	5
Tango	12	0.04%	6
Telegram	11	0.03%	7
Chat On	7	0.02%	8
Hike	5	0.01%	9
Line	4	0.01%	10

It is evident from the Table 1 that chat application whatsapp is being used by all the arts and science college students forming 100% and it ranks top among all the other applications. The second most used chat application is Messenger forming 77% and the third most used chat application is Skype forming 52 %. The other applications namely Hang Outs, We Chat, Tango, Telegram, Chat On, Hike and Line are 18%, 0.04%, 0.04%, 0.03%, 0.02%, 0.01% and 0.01% respectively.

It may be concluded from the above table that there are four chat applications which are popular among arts and science college students. They are Whatsapp, Messenger, Skype and Hang out occupying first, second, third and fourth places respectively. The other chat applications namely Hang Outs, We Chat, Tango, Telegram, Chat On, Hike and Line are being used minimally by arts and science college students.

HYPOTHESIS 2

The time of chatting by Arts and Science College students is equally during all the time of a day.

The details regarding time of chatting by arts and science college students are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS OF ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS TIME OF CHATTING

Time of Chatting	No. of students response	Percentage	Ranking
Night	300	100%	1
Late Night	300	100%	2
Mid Night	276	92%	3
Lunch	257	85.66%	4
Evening	245	81.66%	5
Afternoon	213	71%	6
Morning	123	41%	7
Early Morning	56	18.66%	8

It is evident from the Table 2 that 100% of arts and science college students use mobile chatting during the specified period of Night and Late Night. 92% of students use mobile chatting during Mid Night. 85.66% of students use mobile chatting during the period of Lunch. 81.66% of arts and science college students use mobile chatting during evening hours. 71% of students use mobile chatting in the afternoon hours. 41% of students use mobile chatting during morning hours and 18.66% of students use mobile chatting only in early morning hours.

It may be concluded from the above findings that all the arts and science college students use mobile chatting during Night and Late Night forming 100% with ranking 1 and 2. The Mid Night hours forming 92% ranked third. The remaining periods namely Lunch at 85.66%, Evening 81.66%, Afternoon 71%, Morning 41% and Early Morning at 18.66%.

HYPOTHESIS 3

The Arts and Science College students do chat with all the people associated with them equally.

The details regarding Arts and Science College students' chatting with all the people associated with them are presented in Table 2.

Table 3: PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS OF ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS MOBILE CHATTING WITH WHOM

With Whom	No. of Students	Percentage	Ranking
Friends	300	100%	1
Class Mates	289	96.33%	2
Sisters	113	37.66%	3
Lovers	99	33%	4
Brothers	90	30%	5
Relatives	87	29%	6
Neighbours	23	0.07%	7
Parents	17	0.05%	8
Teachers	11	0.03%	9

It is evident from the Table 3 that 100% of arts and science college students have chat with friends. 96.33% of students have chat with classmates. 37.66% of students have chat with sisters. 33% of students have chat with lovers. 30% of students have chat with brothers. 29% of students have chat with Relatives. Less than 1 % of students have chat with neighbors, parents and teachers.

It may be concluded from the above findings that all the arts and science college students chat with friends forming 100% and placing first priority among the people associated with them. The arts and science college students chat with other people associated with them namely Classmates, Sisters, Lovers, Brothers and Relatives giving priority second, third, fourth and fifth places respectively. The students do have chat with less than 1% with neighbors, parents and teachers.

10. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The following are the findings of the study:

- 1) There are four chat applications which are popular among arts and science college students. They are Whatsapp, Messenger, Skype and Hang out occupying first, second, third and fourth places respectively. The other chat applications namely Hang Outs, We Chat, Tango, Telegram, Chat On, Hike and Line are being used minimally by arts and science college students.
- 2) All the arts and science college students use mobile chatting during Night and Late Night forming 100% with ranking 1 and 2. The Mid Night hours forming 92% ranked third. The remaining periods namely Lunch at 85.66%, Evening 81.66%, Afternoon 71%, Morning 41% and Early Morning at 18.66%.
- 3) All the arts and science college students chat with friends forming 100% and placing first priority among the people associated with them. The arts and science college students chat with other people associated with them namely Classmates, Sisters, Lovers, Brothers and Relatives giving priority second, third, fourth and fifth places respectively. The students do have chat with less than 1% with neighbors, parents and teachers.

11. CONCLUSION

There are four chat applications which are popular among arts and science college students. They are Whatsapp, Messenger, Skype and Hang out occupying first, second, third and fourth places respectively.

All the arts and science college students use mobile chatting during Night and Late Night forming 100% with ranking 1 and 2. The Mid Night hours forming 92% ranked third. The remaining periods namely Lunch at 85.66%, Evening 81.66%, Afternoon 71%, Morning 41% and Early Morning at 18.66%.

All the arts and science college students chat with friends forming 100% and placing first priority among the people associated with them. The arts and science college students chat with other people associated with them namely Classmates, Sisters, Lovers, Brothers and Relatives giving priority second, third, fourth and fifth places respectively.

12. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The finding of the study has brought out the fact that the arts and science college students spend most of the time in chatting. Hence, the educationists may think of designing course materials in text, audio and video form so as to group message through all these chat applications so that useful information will reach the young generation of India. The four chat applications which are popular among arts and science college students namely Whatsapp, Messenger, Skype and Hang out may be used for disseminating subject content by teachers and planners of curriculum. Selection of good friends will ensure proper shaping of children's behavior (Bill Rogers, 2012). It has been proved in many studies. This study is also no exception to that it has proved that the arts and science college students give top priority in chatting to friends. Peer group influence is

top most among all. It is parents who have to govern their children's friends. "Show me your friend I will tell about you" the popular saying has been proved in this study.

13. REFERENCES

- [1] "How mobile messaging apps are changing social behaviour in Asia" *South China Morning Post*: www.scmp.com Published: Friday, 10 April, 2015, 8.00 a.m.
- [2] "Online Chat behaviour tend to follow social norms", *Scientific Report*, May 11, 2012.
- [3] Best, John and Kahn, James V. (1992) "Research in Education" (Sixth Edition), Prentice-Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
- [4] Golden, S. A. R. (2011). *Problems and Prospectus of Distance Learning*. Bharathidhasan University, 343, 344.
- [5] Golden, S. A. R., (2016). *Mobile Subscribers' Satisfaction Towards Offers*. Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities.
- [6] Golden, S. A. R., *MOBILE SUBSCRIBERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS SERVICE TARIFF WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TUTICORIN DIST*, International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah.
- [7] Golden, S. A. R., *SUBSCRIBERS' PREFERENCE TOWARDS MOBILE COMMUNICATION SERVICE-AN ANALYSIS*, International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah.
- [8] Golden, S. A. R., & Regi, S. B. *Mobile Commerce in Modern Business Era*.
- [9] Rogers, Bill (2004) "Classroom Behaviour: A Practical Guide to Effective Teaching Behaviour", Sage Publications, New Delhi
- [10] Rogers, Bill (2004) "How to Manage Children's Challenging Behaviour", Sage Publications, New Delhi.